

Crossing the 10% milestone with ease: Catalytic enrichment of petroleum with second generation bio-based alkanes

News and Views

Katalin Barta

For article (NENERGY-18030504A)

The ever growing usage of fossil transportation fuels contributes to increasing the levels of atmospheric carbon-dioxide globally.^[1] To mitigate the adverse environmental impact caused by these greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions, and to decrease our societies' dependence on non-renewable petroleum, several directives have been put forward worldwide to stimulate the use of liquid energy carriers derived from renewable resources.^[2-4] For example, the European Union aims for a 20% reduction in GHG emission levels by 2020, largely via ensuring that at least 10% of the transportation fuels are bio-based. In the USA, the transportation sector should use up to 36 billion gallons of biofuels, including advanced biofuels, by 2022.^[3]

Bioethanol and biodiesel, typically blended with conventional fuels in various proportions (expressed by E and B values, respectively), represent biofuel alternatives that are already implemented. However, reaching the targeted 10% or higher bioethanol content would require engine modification due to incompatibility issues ('blend-wall').^[4] In addition, both the mentioned biofuels are primarily "first generation" – meaning that they are obtained from edible resources such as corn, sugarcane or vegetable oils and thus may represent a competition with the food supply.^[4,5]

These existing limitations will require a shift toward the use of non-edible second generation resources such as cellulose as well as the identification of suitable targets that would serve as alternative liquid energy carriers: drop-in or emerging biofuels.^[4-6] However, cellulose is a much more challenging substrate due to its recalcitrance and feasible, scalable catalytic approaches are lacking. In order to reach the 10% biofuel target by 2020, new, robust catalytic solutions are urgently required and these evolving technologies need to be compatible with large scale production.^[4]

Writing in Nature Energy – Dusselier, Sels and coworkers describe the production of bio based gasoline from cellulose and lignocellulose in a manner, which not only allows for, but explicitly relies on integration into existing petrochemical refinery schemes.

In a conventional refinery, crude oil is separated into several fractions by distillation. One of these, a low boiling fraction, is the so called Light Straight Run naphtha (LSR) that mainly consists of C5-C6 alkanes. Glucose, the monosaccharide making up cellulose that bears a six carbon atom skeleton, would also turn into C6 alkanes upon exhaustive hydrodeoxygenation (HDO) at reaction temperatures low enough to maintain the C6 connectivity. In their clever approach, the authors propose to use the LSR naphtha cut of petroleum (C5-C6 alkane fraction) itself as part of a biphasic reaction medium in which cellulose is converted to (C6)

alkanes, leading to enrichment of the original alkane mixture with virtually identical, but bio-based components.

Central to this new process, dubbed “Liquid Phase Cellulose-to-Naphtha” (LPCtoN) technology is a biphasic catalytic system that consists of an aqueous and an organic phase (the naphtha cut itself), both incorporating an appropriate catalytic function designed for the above-mentioned multistep cellulose-to alkane conversion. The aqueous layer carries a soluble heteropolyacid catalyst ($H_4SiW_{12}O_{40}$) and is responsible for “cutting” cellulose to smaller monosaccharide units, as well as their further dehydration to mostly furanics such as 5-hydroxymethylfurfural (5-HMF). These cyclic oxygenated intermediates then partition to the organic phase and undergo full HDO to produce C6 alkanes via a series of hydrogenation and dehydration events promoted by a bifunctional acid-metal catalyst (acid modified Ru/C).

Applying the LSR cut to serve as organic phase for the HDO is a remarkable choice by the authors, since one would expect insufficient solubility of the oxygenated intermediates in the apolar alkane phase. Nevertheless, it can be estimated that elevated temperatures markedly increase the solubility of water in hydrocarbons. The authors therefore hypothesised and experimentally confirmed that the ability of the alkanes to efficiently extract oxygenated intermediates will also be enhanced at the reaction temperature (493 K), ensuring high product yields.

Because the alkane mixtures after LPCtoN treatment consist of molecules originating partly from petrochemicals and partly from renewables with largely overlapping compositions, the extent of bio-enrichment was confirmed by using a ^{14}C isotope labelling technique. Since the half-life of the ^{14}C isotope is 5736 years - and crude oil is much older - this measurement only detects carbon atoms derived from fresh biomass. Overall, a 11-18% bio-based carbon enrichment was measured, depending on process conditions.

Since the obtained fuel, enriched with bio-based naphtha consists of mainly linear alkanes, n-hexane being the major component (see Figure 1), its research octane number (RON) is not sufficient, therefore an isomerization step using Pt-loaded ZSM-5 was added. This elevated the RON from an average 50 to 80 and produced the desired bio-enriched fuel that is ready to be blended with other refinery streams to form gasoline.

Notably, the described LPCtoN methodology is compatible with other emerging technologies (“lignin first”) that utilize raw lignocellulose as starting material, thus enabling the utilization of both the lignin and the (hemi)cellulose fractions of lignocellulose. Here, a reductive processing step is performed to obtain aromatic monomers from lignin, while the remaining crude (hemi)cellulose residue is subjected to the LPCtoN process, to give alkane products similar to those obtained with pure cellulose starting materials, albeit with slightly higher C5 alkanes detected due to the hemicellulose present.

In summary, the presented catalytic strategy is elegant as it allows for desired reaction pathways from cellulose to C6 alkanes with minimal C-C bond cleavage, taking advantage of

catalyst compartmentalization in a biphasic reaction media where one of the phases is light naphtha itself. The reaction product is bio-enriched light naphtha, which can be directly integrated into existing infrastructures - this will facilitate possible commercialization. The process scheme – including material balances provided by the authors show promising opportunities for upscaling. Several questions remain to be further addressed, such as catalyst stability and recyclability or the effect of small amounts of bio-based oxygenates on further processing units. Moreover, coupling the hydrodeoxygenation step that uses 80 kg H₂ per ton of carbohydrate with emerging renewable H₂ technologies^[7] may be an interesting future direction. Overall, the results presented here are an exciting step toward achieving the ambitious 10% bio-based carbon target for liquid transportation fuels.

[1] <https://www.epa.gov/ghgemissions/sources-greenhouse-gas-emissions>

[2] https://ec.europa.eu/transport/themes/urban/vehicles/road/biofuels_en

[3] Tyner, W. E. *Biofuels*, **1**(1), 19–21 (2010).

[4] https://www.iea.org/publications/freepublications/publication/2nd_Biofuel_Gen.pdf

[5] Koh, L. P.; Tan, H. T. W; Sodhi, N. S, *Science* **320**, 1419 (2008).

[6] Climent, M. J., Corma, A. & Iborra, S. *Green Chem.* **16**, 516-547 (2014).

[7] Editorial, *Nature Energy*, **1**, Article number: 16127 (2016).